

NOVASOIL

INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODELS FOR SOIL HEALTH

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Preliminary version of tools for analysis of the soil health business models Deliverable D 3.3

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Project Consortium

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Table of contents

List of figures	7
List of tables	7
List of abbreviations	8
Summary	9
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Context of WP 3 objectives	9
1.2 Connection with the other WPs	9
1.3 Purpose and scope of the document.....	10
1.4 Analysis of needs and demands	10
1.5 Process of development	10
2 Conceptual framework.....	11
2.1 DTs framework and connection between the tools.....	12
2.2 Description of the NOVASOIL DTs	13 12
2.2.1 DT 1 Case study current existing incentive analysis	13
2.2.2 DT 2 New incentive analysis.....	16
2.2.3 DT 3 Business model assessment of incentives implementation	19
3. Design of the DTs	20
3.1 Home page	20
3.2 DT 1 Case study current existing incentive analysis.....	22
3.3 Other tools	22
3.4 Log page	23
4 Conclusions.....	24
Resources	26
Acknowledgment.....	27
Annexes	28
Annex 1 – minutes of the technical meetings related to the DTs.....	28

List of figures

Figure 1. NOVASOIL digital toolbox.....	12
Figure 2. Connection between the tools on NOVASOIL DTs	12
Figure 3 Incentives mapping graph.....	14
Figure 4 Frame of the AHP model	18
Figure 5 NOVASOIL DTs architecture.....	20
Figure 6. NOVASOIL DTs home page.....	21
Figure 7 NOVASOIL partners.....	22
Figure 8 Incentives mapping output.....	22
Figure 9 Other NOVASOIL tools.....	23
Figure 10 Log in page.....	23
Figure 11. Registration page	24

List of tables

Table 1 Input for incentives mapping evaluation	13
Table 2 Typology of incentives and their relation to the BMC blocks	14
Table 3 Relation of incentives with the five building blocks of the business model.....	16
Table 4 Lists of factors in 4 categories: strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.....	17
Table 5 Cross-rating of the factors.....	17
Table 6 AHP output.....	19
Table 7 Deriving the weights for the scenarios	19
Table 8 Weights for the incentive from V-AHP considering the financial expenditure for applying the incentive.....	20

Summary

This document reports on tools for analysis of the soil health business models and an overall update on its progress carried out under T 3.3: Tools for analysis of the soil health business models” in the framework of WP3 "Testing and development of a toolbox for incentives" under the NOVASOIL project.

Task 3.3 will build digital tools (DTs) for analysis related to the new incentives based on the information from both WPs 1 and 2, and the results of Task 3.1 and 3.2. In cooperation with WP 5 will be made assessment of possible factors and barriers to the implementation of soil health business models. It will be applied multi-criteria analysis for evaluation of incentives taking into consideration the needed investment as well as SWOT analysis. The aim of the tools is to evaluate different new incentives to rank the most appropriate one for the farmer.

The report presents structure and modules contained in the NOVASOIL DTs for business model incentives. Also, it is presented the applied user-friendly architecture of the NOVASOIL DTs for existing, new incentives and its estimation connected with soil health business models.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context of WP 3 objectives

The objective of the task T 3.3: Tools for analysis of the soil health business models to make digital tools for evaluation of business model incentives.

The digital tools are developed as a web-based digital tool because this approach has advantages as live update, lack of client-server infrastructure and customer access without a marketplace as intermediary. The interface will be responsive for telephones and tablets.

1.2 Connection with the other WPs

Connection with WP 1 and WP2: Information will be provided based on the lessons learned from the key actors and stakeholders.

Connection with WP3: It will be used analysis applied and verified under tasks T3.1 and T3.2.

Connection with WP5: T 3.3 will be shared with the audience, including the Communities of Practice in cooperation with WP 5.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the document

Deliverable D 3.3 Preliminary version of tools for analysis of the soil health business models aims to define the NOVASOIL digital tools for analysis of new incentives, which is part of T 3.3: Tools for analysis of the soil health business models. It is presented as a preliminary framework of digital tools for soil health business models.

1.4 Analysis of needs and demands

NOVASOIL toolbox will be co-designed with potential end-users and CoP community. In this regard, the conceptual design and features of the toolbox was discussed during the CoP event organised in 12/12/2023 in collaboration with WP5. The event was streamed by YouTube and Google Meet platform (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5d_eqcDhbf4).

A brief introduction was conducted by Mr. Luis Sanchez Álvarez, Policy Officer of the NOVASOIL project, who framed the project within the environmental and development objectives set by the European Union.

Needs and demands identified in a previous research work were discussed, highlighting the barriers to implement business models that promote soil health. Lack of financial resources, lack of interest by end consumers and lack of information were the main barriers confirmed by the audience. As well as the contract length preferences per land use type (agricultural, forestry and urban), identifying the need of reduce the bureaucratic burden of the process.

The event concluded with an online questionnaire where participants could identify what kind of potential tool-box features are more interesting for each one.

Geographical information' access, open and transparent documentation, different scenarios, suggested alternatives and support were some features requested by the end-users.

The participants remarked the open access and free to this kind of tools and evaluate the economic viability of the different business models.

Considering, their needs and demands, and the comments received during the event, EVENOR, as project coordinator, will explore the best way to develop other tools. The aim is to cover the most of need and demands requested in parallel with the tool-box signed in the GA. For that, a data management module which will compile data generated during the project and connected with the main open repositories may be developed to promote its use.

1.5 Process of development

The overall process of development of the DTs tools for soil health business models included several steps: discussion with NOVASOIL partners regarding core elements of the DTs, discussion and drafting of the structure, selection of service provider, development of graphic design and page title, preliminary digital version of the DTs for soil health business models.

In order to identify the core elements of the DTs, several meetings were organised in 2024. Those internal meetings allowed to discuss and define different categories for the future DTs.

The first discussion was organized on 30 January 2024 when the DTs structure was discussed with the coordinator of the NOVASOIL project – EVENOR.

Then, it was organized a technical meeting for all partners on 08 February 2024. There were discussed some main aspects such as main points in the design, tools, and further steps to test the tools. Minutes of the meeting is presented in Annex 1.

For that, in parallel, additional tool for data management and processing will be developed based on the NOVASOIL' datasets expected and the main open repositories. Soil health, environmental and economic variables will be included in the final version.

2 Conceptual framework

The WP3 is focusing on a toolbox development. It contains three major components (fig. 1). The preliminary version of the first tool – digital hub of knowledge – was presented in D3.2 Preliminary version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models (Nikolov et al. 2023b).

The focus of this deliverable is the second component – Digital tools for soil health business models.

The third component of the toolbox is going to be prepared in the upcoming months in the frame of task 3.5 Decision support tool for soil health business models.

Stepping on the current WP 3 results, the second component of digital tools should help the user to choose the most appropriate incentives based on the internal, external environment, and costs for implementation.

Figure 1. NOVASOIL digital toolbox

2.1 DTs framework and connection between the tools

The NOVASOIL DTs is unique instrument which evaluates the appropriate new incentives based on multicriteria analysis, taking into consideration the business model of the entity, its external and internal environment, and the needed investment for incentives' implementation.

The goal of DTs is to support the choose of the most appropriate incentives taking into consideration mapping and gap analysis of existing incentives, the SWOT and multicriteria analysis and the costs for implementation (fig. 2).

The DTs for soil health business models includes three main tools:

- DT 1 Case study current incentive analysis;
- DT 2 New incentive analysis;
- DT 3 Business model assessment of incentives implementation.

The user should make a registration to be able to perform and to revise the analyses.

Figure 2. Connection between the tools on NOVASOIL DTs

All components of the DTs will be tested with real data. Also, the tools will be presented to stakeholders. The tools will be adjusted based on the stakeholder feedback. The use of DTs to evaluate incentives can be done individually or on a multi-stakeholder consensus basis.

Multi-stakeholder consensus basis is recommended approach for DT 1 and DT 2, because ensures more comprehensive assessment of the applied incentives and new incentives choice considering the local conditions in each case.

An individual approach is recommended for DT 3 Business model assessment of incentives' implementation, because the assessment of the analyzed new incentives impact on the elements of the business model in a specific entity.

2.2 Description of the NOVASOIL DTs

As it was mentioned above, the NOVASOIL Digital tools for soil health business models contain three tools for incentives' evaluation.

2.2.1 DT 1 Case study current existing incentive analysis

This tool is focused on evaluation of the current incentives and identifying the gaps taking into consideration the business model of the farm.

The incentives mapping aims to categorize incentives that have been implemented within the agricultural and forestry sector to promote soil health business models, encompassing social, economic, and environmental aspects.

For the incentives mapping was applied the methodology defined in D3.1 – Report on mapping existing incentives for sustainable soil health business models (Nikolov et al. 2023a). It was adopted tailormade Business Model Canvas (BMC) to evaluate the incentives effects to the farmer's business model.

The needed input for the current incentives mapping is presented on table 1. The user should complete their evaluation of the presented components for all currently applied incentives.

Table 1 Input for incentives mapping evaluation

Incentives	Soil health influence	Influence over soil health strategy		Soil health business model/Case study				
		Fertilization	Remediation	Customer value proposition (Scale 1 to 3)	Channels and partnerships (Scale 1 to 3)	Revenue and cost structure (Scale 1 to 3)	Key resources (Scale 1 to 3)	Key activities (Scale 1 to 3)
Name	Low, Medium, High	Yes/ No	Yes/ No	Low, Medium, High	Low, Medium, High	Low, Medium, High	Low, Medium, High	Low, Medium, High

The output of the analysis would be as it is presented on figure 3.

Figure 3 Incentives mapping graph

In addition, the gap analysis of the current incentives aims to identify the new opportunities for the farmer, identifying the gaps in the currently applied incentives' influence on the soil health business model elements.

The new incentives will be chosen by the users on their own depending on the region. These incentives should be linked to the incentives categories described in table 2 (FAO classification).

Each incentive category is related to two of the BMC building blocks (table 2, the cells in green colour).

Table 2 Typology of incentives and their relation to the BMC blocks

Category of incentives		Business Model Canvas building blocks				
		Customer value proposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost	Key resources	Key activities
Policy-driven	1.1 Prohibition of use					
	1.2 Property use rights					
	1.3 Taxes/charges					
	1.4 Mandatory farm set-asides					
	1.5 Subsidies					
	1.6 Conservation easements					
	1.7 Permits and quotas					

Category of incentives	Business Model Canvas building blocks				
	Customer value proposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost	Key resources	Key activities
1.8 Marketing labels (certificates/sustainability standards)					
1.9 Offsets					
1.10 Impact funds					
1.11 Responsible sourcing of agriculture products and services					
1.12 Corporate social responsibility					
Voluntary	2.1 Green bonds				
	2.2 Voluntary farm set-asides				
	2.3 Conservation concessions				
	2.4 Direct Payment for Ecosystem Services				
	2.5 Rewards for Ecosystem Services				
	2.6 Marketing labels (without certificates or standards)				

Source: Adapted to Table 2 in Deliverable 3.1

The gap analysis has the following process (table 3):

- The user completes all incentives that are currently applied and defines the incentive's category based on table 2. The tool gives back the impacted BMC blocks. Based on the results (**current gaps**) the user could identify those areas of the business model that are not affected by the applied incentives.
- The user completes new incentives and the incentive's category. The tool gives back recommendation if the incentive is appropriate or not in terms of the business model influence. It could be an iterative process which identifies several appropriate new incentives.
- The analysis should propose the potential incentives corresponding to their business model. The analysis can be done by a farmer or group which includes relevant stakeholders. In this format it should be discussed and proposed the new incentives based on stakeholder's feedback. When discussing the new incentives, if their number is more than three, it is necessary to make a ranking of the incentives in order to select only three. Each one of the participants can have three votes

for the proposed incentives. The three incentives with the highest score will be the selected (they will be used in the next phase – the AHP model).

Table 3 Relation of incentives with the five building blocks of the business model

Incentives	Category of incentives	Business Model Canvas building blocks					Rank
		Customer value proposition	Channels and partnerships	Revenue and cost	Key resources	Key activities	
Current incentive 1							
Current incentive 2							
Current incentive 3							
New Incentive 1							
New Incentive 2							
New Incentive 3							
New Incentive 4							

Source: The authors

2.2.2 DT 2 New incentive analysis

The purpose of DT 2 is to evaluate new incentives that could affect those areas that are not affected by the currently applied incentives according to the DT 1 results.

The user should suggest new incentives that they are interested in. The tool suggests incentives that are appropriate to fill the identified gaps – the building blocks that are not covered by the currently applied incentives. It will be used the categorization of Garrett and Neves (2016) that was used in D3.1 (Nikolov et al., 2023a).

To ensure that the evaluation of the incentives will be as close as possible to the actual problems and opportunities of the investigated farm the methodology combines SWOT analysis and Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) analysis.

The role of the SWOT analysis is to derive the criteria for evaluating the incentives. On the second stage of the methodology, the adequacy and usefulness of the gaps from DT 1 will be evaluated through the AHP analysis.

SWOT analysis

The user should identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. To support that process, four lists of factors have to be created by the evaluator:

1. List of potential strengths;
2. List of potential weaknesses;
3. List of potential opportunities;
4. List of potential threats.

In table 4 an example visualization of the four lists is given.

Table 4 Lists of factors in 4 categories: strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats

Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
Factor 1	Factor 1	Factor 1	Factor 1
Factor 2	Factor 2	Factor 2	Factor 2
.....
Factor n	Factor n	Factor n	Factor n

On the next stage of the implementation of the SWOT analysis, the farmer must evaluate each factor from the group's strengths and weaknesses against each factor from the group's opportunities and threats. The process is visualized in table 5.

Table 5 Cross-rating of the factors

		Opportunities			Threats		
		Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Strengths	Factor 1	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating
	Factor 2	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating
	Factor 3	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating
Weaknesses	Factor 1	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating
	Factor 2	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating
	Factor 3	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating	Rating

The evaluation is made on 3 point scale and in case there are more than one evaluator the final grade summarizes the individual grades.

The tool automatically sums the factor scores by rows and by columns. Thus, within each group of factors (opportunities, threats, strengths, weaknesses), the factor with the highest score can be determined. These factors are used to feed the AHP analysis.

AHP analysis

On the second stage, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is applied to estimate the importance of the incentives that has been defined in tool 1.

The Analytical Hierarchical Process is widely used for estimating the alternative business models and its components. It is also common to use case studies in order to study business models and use AHP estimation of the components of the models. AHP can help with weighing of various alternatives according to a set of criteria, when the influences between alternatives and criteria are hierarchical.

The next step is to make pairwise comparison of the alternatives per criterion. The process is visualized in figure 4.

Source: Authors' figure

Figure 4 Frame of the AHP model

The number of criteria and alternatives depend on the case. The user decides how much, and which are the criteria and alternatives.

The **goal** of the analysis is the evaluation of the incentives.

The alternatives in the model are the incentives derived from the DTI. The criteria are the factors with the highest rating from the application of SWOT analysis.

Criteria:

- ✓ Factor 1

- ✓ Factor 2
- ✓ Factor 3
- ✓ Factor 4

Alternatives:

- ✓ Incentive 1
- ✓ Incentive 2
- ✓ Incentive 3

Based on the criteria and alternatives thus derived, a questionnaire is visualized. The questionnaire is visualized in the software, where the participants should put a rating from 1/9 to 9. The rating in the proposed analysis can be done individually or based on consensus if there is more than one participant.

The output of the analysis is ranking the incentives based on the SWOT analysis evaluation (table 6).

Table 6 AHP output

	AHP
Incentive 1	20%
Incentive 2	30%
Incentive 3	50%

2.2.3 DT 3 Business model assessment of incentives implementation

The V-AHP method combines the use of the AHP decision-making method based on multi-criteria analysis with the "Lean" method. The Lean method is used by weighing the results of AHP with the costs necessary to implement the relevant business model. In this way, the subjective ratings are combined with an objective quantifier to produce the final rating score (Compagno et al., 2013).

Every incentive is a different scenario for the user. As an input, the user should make estimation of the necessary investment for each scenario. Based on this, estimation weights are derived (table 7).

Table 7 Deriving the weights for the scenarios

	Estimation	Weights
Incentive 1 (Scenario 1)	XXXXXX EUR	0.2
Incentive 2 (Incentive 1)	XXXXXX EUR	0.4
Incentive 3 (Incentive 1)	XXXXXX EUR	0.4

The result (table 8) is derived by combining the weights from table 6 with the result of the AHP application (table 6). The output from V-AHP is visualized in table 7.

Table 8 Weights for the incentive from V-AHP considering the financial expenditure for applying the incentive

	V-AHP
Incentive 1	15%
Incentive 2	40%
Incentive 3	45%

3. Design of the DTs

The architecture of the demo version of the DTs for soil health business models has the structure presented on figure 5.

Figure 5 NOVASOIL DTs architecture

3.1 Home page

The home page is design and structure are the same as the one on the NOVASOIL digital hub of knowledge (DHK). The aim is the tool to be recognized by the public as a NOVASOIL's one.

The home page opens when the user writes or click on the DTs link. Also, the home page is opening when the user clicks on the NOVASOIL logo on the left-up corner of the page.

The first thing that the user sees is the name of the DTs – digital tools for soil health business models – and short description of it (fig. 6).

Figure 6. NOVASOIL DTs home page

On this page the user could find information about the tool, short description of and link to the NOVASOIL project page, and the NOVASOIL project partners logos (fig. 6). The footnote on each page contains newsletter sign-up, links to the main menu, and contact information (fig. 7).

Figure 7 NOVASOIL partners

3.2 DT 1 Case study current existing incentive analysis

The user should evaluate the influence of the currently applied incentives to the elements of the soil health business models, using a drop-down menu. The output of the analysis is incentives mapping is visualised using by a graph shown on figure 8.

Figure 8 Incentives mapping output

3.3 Other tools

The other tools menu provides a short description of the NOVASOIL TOOLBOX and links to all its components – Digital Hub of knowledge, Digital tools for soil health models, and Decision support tool.

Figure 9 Other NOVASOIL tools

3.4 Log page

The log in area includes username and password (fig. 10).

Figure 10 Log in page

In terms of registration (fig. 11), the user should complete information about:

- Names
- Age group: 18-29; 30-39; 40-49; 50-59; 60-69; +70;
- Gender: female; male; no binary; I prefer not to answer;
- User: farmer; policy maker; researcher; industry and supply chain actors; NGOs and civil society; landowners; consumers; other – specify.
- Country:
- e-mail
- password and re-enter the password.

The screenshot shows the 'Registration Form' on the Novasoil website. The form is set against a background image of a green field. It contains several input fields and radio button options. The 'Names*' field is a text box. The 'Country*' field is a dropdown menu with 'Select an option' and a downward arrow. The 'Age' section has radio buttons for '18-29', '30-39', '40-49', '50-59', '60-69', and '70+'. The 'Gender' section has radio buttons for 'Female', 'Male', 'No binary', and 'I prefer not to answer'. The 'Type of the user*' section is a list box with options: 'Farmers', 'Policy makers', 'Researchers', 'Industry and supply chain actors', 'NGOs and civil society', 'Landowners', 'Consumers', and 'Other'. Below this list is a text input field for 'Specify:'. The 'E-mail*', 'Password*', and 'Re-enter Password*' fields are text boxes. At the bottom left of the form, there is a note: '* - Mandatory' and 'Please select type'. The footer of the page features the European Union flag and the text: 'Funded by the European Union. Grant agreement ID: 101091268'.

Figure 11. Registration page

4 Conclusions

Deliverable 3.3 presents the preliminary version of the NOVASOIL DTs for soil health business models. The suggested DTs provide different experience to the users evaluating the new incentives considering the environment of the user the implementation costs.

The functionality is described based on three digital tools: DT 1 Case study current incentive analysis; DT 2 New incentive analysis; and DT 3 Business model assessment of incentives implementation. In addition, it is presented the design of NOVASOIL DTs.

This deliverable sets the foundation for D 3.8 Report on final version of tools for analysis of the soil health business models due in M32.

Resources

1. Nikolov D., Tzvetanova E., Boevsky I., Banov M., Kostenarov K., Todorova K. (2023b) NOVASOIL D3.2 Preliminary version of the knowledge hub for soil health business models
2. Nikolov D., Tzvetanova E., Boevsky I., Banov M., Kostenarov K., Marinova, Ts. (2023a) NOVASOIL D3.1 – Report on mapping existing incentives for sustainable soil health business models
3. Garrett, L. and Neves, B. (2016) Incentives for Ecosystem Services: Spectrum. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, Italy
4. Compagno, L., D'Urso, D., Latora, A. G., Trapani, N. (2013). The Value-Analytic Hierarchy Process: A Lean Multi Criteria Decision Support Method. *Manufacturing Modelling, Management and Control*, 7(1), 875-880. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.3182/20130619-3-RU-3018.00573>

Acknowledgment

Annexes

Annex 1 – minutes of the technical meetings related to the DTs Minutes

Meeting held on 08 February 2024

List of participants

Eriselda Canaj, Merili Toom, Fabio Bartolini, Merili Toom, Francisco José Blanco Velázquez, Dimitre Nikolov, Ekatherina Tzvetanova, Toms Lazdins, Dania Baldoni, Barbora Nohlová, Ivan Boevsky, Catriona Willoughby, Luciano Pagano, Carina Obergröbner, Francesco Riccioli, Ferdinand Lang, Greta Winkler, Tiina Köster, Alexandra Langlais-Hesse, Kerttu Tammik, Gloria Minarelli, Luca Contrino, Insa Thiermann, Kalvi Tamm

Agenda

Discussion on digital tools for soil health business models under T3.3.

Notes - Digital tools for soil health business models

The design of the digital tools will be in line with the project design – color palette, fonts, and so on.

The DTs web-based tool will have links and information regarding the project and the NOVASOIL digital hub of knowledge.

The DTs will include three DTs focused on incentives evaluation.

The partners were interested in the applied methods and the activities that they will take part in in the next following months regarding this task. The details regarding information and process and the process will be determined soon. Then, it will be sent an instruction. The NBU team is ready to hold one-to-one meetings and technical meetings for all partners.

The recording of the meeting was uploaded in the NOVASOIL Google Drive if other partners have some feedback. It was not received any comments.